

Research Article

Mountain bike trails in urban forests: Meeting recreation demands in Vienna and Zurich

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ABSTRACT

The forests around urban centers are vulnerable to deforestation due to climate change and high societal pressure for recreation. Vienna and Zurich, with populations of approximately two million and 500,000, respectively, exemplify these issues. Both cities are growing, tourism is increasing and forest managers have struggled over recreational infrastructures. Higher urbanization has led to overcrowded urban forest areas and conflicts between the ecosystem services they provide. Mountain biking has developed rapidly in recent years, and the related urban pressure is high.

While some solutions have been found, the question remains as to how sustainable these solutions are in terms of stability and resistance to future challenges. This study investigates the struggles related to the recreational use of urban forests, focusing on illegal mountain bike trails and the response to emerging societal demands from both stakeholders and decision-makers. Using Vienna and Zurich's forests as examples, the research first traces the struggles and related negotiations for the legalization of bike trails back to their origins. Second, it explores the solutions found, and third, it assesses the changes and resulting future demands. Data sources include documents and semi-structured interviews with key actors involved, including bikers and forest managers. Our consideration of bikers and forest managers shows differences and commonalities in actor compositions, planning strategies and outcomes. The most decisive factor for infrastructure installments is organization of pressure from interest groups to influence change. However, the financial solutions require better alignment. It appears questionable whether the trails in their current state can respond to and fulfill growing demands and adapt to current technical innovation in the sports sector. The results provide insights for future efforts on how to govern and manage increasing pressure from urban populations on sports activities within nearby forest areas.

Management implications

- Urban mountain biking is rapidly growing around metropolitan areas and should be recognized as a management concern by public authorities.
- Legalizing mountain bike trails can generate sustainable income for landowners and municipalities.
- Vienna's funding challenges emphasize the need for public investment, while Zurich's case showed that public funding improved maintenance but reduced biker autonomy. Managers should balance these tensions.

- High costs of self-managing legal mountain biking trails, as in Vienna, suggest the need for alternative support.
- Incorporating bikers' perspectives in management is essential for resolving conflicts over illegal trails.
- Bottom-up, collaborative approaches are necessary for managing complex urban forest recreation challenges.

1. Introduction

Steered by climate change impacts in cities and increasing societal demands, the importance and portfolio of forest-based ecosystem

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services have expanded significantly across Europe in recent decades (Orsi et al., 2020; Primmer et al., 2021). While climate change itself leads to considerable damages and vulnerability in forests (Romeiro et al., 2022), forests provide habitats that increase biodiversity, sequester carbon, decrease soil erosion, secure clean water, and supply timber and material for chemical and energy product uses (Forest Europe, 2020). In terms of direct societal benefits, forests provide outdoor recreation (Agimass et al., 2018; Frick et al., 2018), particularly around the urban centers and metropolitan areas (Wilkes-Allemann et al., 2017). Deng et al. (2017) found that visitors and residents generally hold positive perceptions of urban forests for leisure purposes, with recreational aspects being particularly important. Although outdoor recreation is valued in everyday life in urban society (Bell et al., 2009; Mann and Absher, 2008; Mann et al., 2010), it can pose major challenges to forest managers and authorities (Wilkes-Allemann et al., 2022). Over time, the recreational use of urban forests has expanded. Formerly, recreation was mainly connected with rest, relaxation, and solitude (Arnberger, 2006); nowadays, adventure- and experience-oriented activities like mountain biking, foraging, paragliding, climbing and jogging are also included (Burgin & Hardiman, 2012; Zivojinovic et al., 2020). The challenges for urban administration and forest managers range from legal liability, financing, and forest and infrastructure maintenance, as well as issues around environmental and landscape protection (Miller et al., 2015). Recent studies on mountain biking in rural Switzerland have shown that efforts to increase stakeholder involvement are useful for facing these challenges (Wilkes-Allemann & Ludvig, 2019). However, these studies did not consider the steady increase in technical requirements for new trails and the rise in innovation trends such as e-biking in urban mountainous regions. Another decisive factor is access and utilization rights.

In Austria and Switzerland, outdoor recreational activities are generally available free of charge, and both countries uphold the right to enter private and public forests under certain conditions (Austrian Forest Law, 2002; Swiss Civil Code, 1907, Art. 699). Historically, forest roads (provided for harvesting wood) have served as the initial setting for recreational activities like hiking, jogging and dog walking (Rupf, 1961). Switzerland has implicitly permitted mountain biking on forest roads by legal interpretation, while in Austria, it is the forest owners who are responsible for maintaining forest roads, and they must by law explicitly authorize all biking. Our Austrian case example had such permitted forest roads as the official and sole legalized mountain bike trail net around the city (referred to as Phase I in the remainder of this article).

However, the number of bikers had increased (Koemle & Morawetz, 2016). A combination of the rapid technical development and newly emerging trends in riding styles (Zajc & Berzelak, 2016) renders forest roads in general less attractive for many contemporary bikers (Taylor & Sand, 2021). This includes even families with children. As a consequence, mountain bikers have created illegal trails outside forest roads and across forest areas.

On the one hand, such developments pose new challenges in terms of financing and liability for forest owners and forest managers; on the other hand, new environmental concerns have emerged (Taylor & Sand, 2021). In addition, these developments lead to conflicts among different forest users in urban forests, such as bikers, hikers and dog walkers (Arnberger, 2006; Bakhtiaria et al., 2014; Kleiner et al., 2022; Seeland et al., 2002; Wilkes-Allemann et al., 2015).

The legal differences between forest utilization practices, such as harvesting and biking, are so far understudied. While harvesting is the right of the forest owners (Austrian Forest Programme, 2007; Swiss National Forest Programme, 2004), mountain biking is not explicitly included in the lists of usage rights.

Thus far, retrospective legalization of such use of forest-based infrastructure has been highly contested. This is because it leads to more conflicts among the different parties involved and because trade-offs between different forest functions (e.g., harvesting versus

recreation activities) have to be negotiated, causing extra costs. Analyzing the actions and decision-making processes behind such trade-offs may help in identifying synergies for improving the management of urban forests for the well-being of all (Dennis et al., 2016).

So far, use options of limited natural resources have been investigated under the theoretical framework of social-ecological innovations (Dennis et al., 2016). Dennis et al. (2016) demonstrated how resource management decisions in horticultural and silvicultural space management must be diversified and made polycentric to respond to social and ecological challenges of urbanization. With a focus on recreational activities, Jay and Schraml (2012) highlighted the difficulties that such new governance approaches entail for forest managers and their concerns.

Conceptually, we use the notion of social innovation to theorize the role that actors' involvement can play for successful negotiations between the interest groups to legalize existent illegal mountain bike trails (MBTs). We use the term "social innovation" for a novel solution to an existing problem that is not technically solved but through new social (re-) configurations and the shifting of power relations (Howaldt & Kopp, 2012). While Dennis et al. (2016) used technical mapping via geospatial data to examine stakeholder responses to local conditions, our research include activists' and forest managers' perspectives on the interactions and their opinions on the quality of the outcomes of responses to urban societal demands.

We are interested in the quality of stakeholder interactions in the search for a common solution. Social innovation entails the strong role of civil society actors in "collective processes," with the normative goal of finding new mutual solutions to societal problems (Sinclair & Baglioni, 2014).

Therefore, in this article, we aim to understand the specific responses that lead to the provision of mountain bike trails by identifying the stakeholders involved and the outcomes of their interactions. The research questions we are addressing focus on tracing and comparing specific solution outcomes: Which stakeholder groups (actors' types, interests and concerns) were involved in the decision-making process, and how? How was a workable agreement reached in the decision-making process? How sustainable are the results with respect to future demands? Our analysis centers on two remarkable decision-making processes for the provision of urban mountain bike trails in forests.

In what follows, we outline the theoretical framework for conceptualizing the social innovation processes in terms of actors' involvement (Section 2) and materials and methods (Section 3), as well as the results in terms of genesis of the process, main catalyst for starting the process, stakeholders' interactions and the main outcomes of the interactions (Section 4). The following two sections discuss the results in light of our research questions (Section 5) as well as the principal conclusions, including recommendations for future research (Section 6).

2. Theoretical framework

Scholarly literature addressing contemporary societal problems has employed the term "social innovation" as a determining factor (Howaldt & Kopp, 2012; Mulaert, 2013; Mulgan, 2007; Sinclair & Baglioni, 2014). Essential components of social innovation are the reconfiguration of social relations and the strong role of civil society actors (Polman et al., 2017). Howaldt and Kopp (2012) define social innovation as "a new combination and/or new configuration of social practices in certain areas of action or social contexts prompted by certain actors or constellations of actors in an intentional targeted manner with the goal of better satisfying or answering needs and problems than is possible on the basis of established practices" (p. 44).

Most authors defining the concept describe "new arrangements" linked to societal needs, problems and changes (Bock, 2012; Cajariba-Santana, 2014; European Union, 2014; Hämäläinen and Heiskala, 2007; Howaldt & Kopp, 2012; Phills et al., 2008; Pol & Ville, 2009; Sinclair & Baglioni, 2014). The type of social innovations we are investigating in

relation to forest-based recreational infrastructure provisioning is driven by three structuring topics:

1. Innovation development
2. Maintenance and funding
3. Future prospects and sustainability of outcomes

Innovation development addresses the inclusion of actors in decision-making processes. These actors can differ from those usually involved in public policymaking (Dery, 1984; Dye, 1977, 2008). The research applies the concept of “governance,” emerging from the 1990s, which involves a nonhierarchical process of governing wherein particular non-state, private corporate and civil society actors participate in and negotiate the formulation of public policy (Mayntz, 1998; Mayntz & Scharpf, 1995; Ostrom, 1990; Rhodes, 1997). This cooperation between various actors has been emphasized as taking place in different forms within mixed networks of public and private actors (Mayntz, 2003). We will inquire into these relations in the context of the highly conflictful negotiations around illegal mountain bike trails.

Maintenance and funding strategies for mountain bike trails are crucial for their sustainability and effectiveness for at least two reasons: First, maintaining mountain bike trails is expensive, and clarifying who will cover these costs during the negotiation process is essential. Second, effective maintenance and funding strategies require the involvement of multiple stakeholders.

Future prospects and sustainability of mountain bike trails hinges on the continuous involvement of stakeholders and the adaptability of the trails to evolving recreational demands and technical innovations in the sport. Ensuring long-term stability requires not only adequate funding and maintenance strategies but also proactive management to address potential environmental impacts and conflicts with other forest users.

Many involved stakeholders from the forestry sector, such as hunters or forest owners, would presumably prefer to forbid the use of forests for such purposes. Therefore, our research relates to the factors that enable stakeholders who normally would not communicate with each other to engage in negotiations for finding mutual solutions. In the cases of Vienna and Zurich, it was impossible to prohibit mountain biking through legal means and executive force due to a high demand. This makes them particularly interesting.

The study investigates the precise nature of “response to societal demands” at the empirical level, exploring how best-practice solutions are found in times of limited forest resources and increasing societal pressure. We use the expectations and promises of the notion of social innovation, going beyond its ambiguities and sometimes even “vagueness” (Grimm et al., 2013) by applying it on empirical examples. Following this, we argue that social innovation can introduce a societal dimension to ecological studies in forestry. For our two case studies, it is crucial to examine the solutions found for addressing these highly conflictful situations and stakeholder pressures.

3. Material, methods and cases

3.1. Case description and selection

Our research used qualitative empirical data, delving into the characteristics of two cases from a social science perspective that emphasizes the importance of practical knowledge and experiences in concrete economic developments and activities (Gerring, 2006). We employed a qualitative method for our research, as it allows for an in-depth exploration of the complex interactions and negotiations among stakeholders involved in the legalization of mountain bike trails. This approach is justified because it provides a comprehensive understanding of the social dynamics and practical experiences in focus.

The cases were selected based on their relevance in the context of social innovation, their proximity to big cities, and the high frequentation of the trails (Gerring, 2004). We chose a qualitative, small-N design

(Yin, 2009) in two similar cases (Lijphart, 1999). Hence, both cases meet the criteria of urban forestry area, high usage frequency, similar opposition to the trails, and similar groups of stakeholders and serve as exemplary cases: Biketrail Triemli for Zurich and the WienerWaldTrails for Vienna (Table 1).

The Biketrail Triemli¹ is situated in the canton of Zurich, next to a mountain called Uetliberg or Hausberg of Zurich (Fig. 1). The trail is 3.5 km long and is situated in publicly owned forest land, primarily owned by the city of Zurich (Table 1). At the start of the negotiation process, bikers were allowed to use the local train to reach the trail’s starting point. Today, bikers are no longer allowed to use the train and have to push their bikes or ride them to the top of the mountain in order to be able to use the trail. The trail is a single track, meaning that only bikers are allowed to use it.

The WienerWaldTrails² are located in the northeastern section of the Vienna woods (Wienerwald), encompassing the Sophienalpe, a small mountain (alp) in the province of Lower Austria (Fig. 1). Part of the forested area where the WienerWaldTrails are located belongs to a UNESCO Biosphere Reserve. Before the WienerWaldTrails were legalized, there was an existing road network for biking on forest roads, developed beginning in the 1990s and known as Phase I (Table 1). This network has 44 routes, totaling 1000 km, with a total elevation difference of approximately 2000 m, and is located solely on official forest roads with the agreement of forest owners, thus having no conflict potential. However, these routes lost attractiveness due to changes in the sport. The legalized trails established in Phase II, beginning in 2014, comprise nine trails with a total length of 14 km and an elevation difference of 1400 m. Among these nine trails from Phase II, seven are “shared trails,” meaning that bikers and hikers both use these trails. Fig. 2 (above) illustrates the trails of Phase II.

As shown in Figs. 1 and 2, the selected trails are located in forests very close to highly populated metropolitan areas.

3.2. Data collection and analysis

Data were collected between September 2018 and May 2023, aiming to cover the entire process of decision-making, installation and maintenance.

We identified the key actors involved via web-based search and their mentioning in newspaper articles. Some of the principal activists and founders were interviewed multiple times (Table 2). To collect data, a total of eight in-depth, long-term semi-structured interviews were conducted and analyzed using the method of qualitative content analysis (Bauer, 2000; Mayring, 2010). For understanding the context and to prepare the interview guides, a range of documents, such as the forest acts and ordinances, forest management plans, a feasibility study, brochures on both trails and the status report of the Vienna Biosphere Reserve were used in respect to their specific mentioning of recreational use, problematic circumstances and response by stakeholders.

The categories for the interview guide (see Supplementary Material to this article) were structured as followed:

- Negotiation process, actors involved, interests, and concerns
- Funding mechanisms, maintenance of the trails and future prospects of financing
- Different interests during the process
- Future prospects of the trail

The subsequent analysis (Weber, 1985) aimed at answering the research questions outlined in the introduction. We chose content

¹ <https://schweizmobil.ch/en/place-of-interest-711-biketrail-triemli> [last access 2023-07-20], see Fig. 1, Illustration by Sylvannisa Nina Putri.

² <https://www.wienerwaldtrails.at/> [last access 2023-07-20], see Fig. 2, Illustration by Sylvannisa Nina Putri.

Table 1
Main features of selected case studies (source: compiled by authors).

Region	Trail name	Length (km)	Difference in altitude (m)	Type of trail	Forest ownership
Zürich (CH)	Biketrail Triemli	3.5	350	Single track only for bikers	City of Zurich (375 ha), ETH Zurich (190 ha) (Eidgenössische Technische Hochschule Zürich)
Vienna (AT)	WienerWaldTrails	Phase I: 1000 Phase II: 14 (in addition to Phase I)	Phase I: 2000 Phase II: 1400	Phase I: ^a 44 permitted trails on forest roads. Phase II: 9 trails (7 shared trails with hikers, two single tracks only for bikers)	City of Vienna, Austrian Federal Forest Company, Klosterneuburg Monastery, some small private owners

^a As shown in Table 1, the WienerWaldTrails are characterized by two phases. Phase I includes forest roads where mountain biking was officially allowed. As outlined in the introduction to this paper and reflected upon by our interview partners, these roads were not attractive any longer and led to the negotiations in Phase II.

Fig. 1. The triemli trail in Zurich as of August 2023.

analysis for the transcribed texts because it enables the determination of the presence of content, themes and concepts within qualitative data in a transparent manner. We followed the line of questions through the texts and compared the content of the answers of each interviewee. The method provides a systematic approach to the analysis that other researchers can replicate.

The following key topics for analysis were applied: (i) genesis of the process, (ii) main catalyst for starting the negotiations, (iii) stakeholder types and stakeholders' interests and concerns, (iv) main results in terms of negotiation outcome, (v) monetary funding strategies and (vi) future prospects.

Interviewees were selected based on their level of involvement in the activities (Table 2). In the Swiss case, two biker representatives (one is a founder and member of Züritrails, who was interviewed twice during the research period, and the other is a representative of the Swiss Competence Centre for Accident Prevention) and a representative of public administration from Grün Stadt Zürich, which is today the forest owner

of the forest area, were interviewed. In the Austrian case, two founding members of the WienerWaldTrails (interviewed twice during the research period), a representative of the main forest owner organization involved (Austrian State Forests, Öbf), and the main representative of the management of the UNESCO-Austrian Wienerwald Biosphere Reserve were interviewed. All founding members were interviewed at least twice over a period of five years. After the initial round of data collection, we came back to these principal stakeholders for further verification of the results. This should help to increase the reliability of our data as we wanted to make sure that we interpreted the opinions on the process correctly. An interview guide, including 20 open-ended questions, was used and further adapted to the specific interview partners (see Supplementary Material to this article). For the subsequent rounds of interviews, questions on lessons learned and future maintenance were added.

Fig. 2. The WienerWaldTrails Phase II in the Vienna woods as of August 2023.

Table 2
Details of interviews (source: compiled by authors).

Case	Code	Representative of	Level of involvement	Role for data collection	Year and duration of interview
Zurich	ZI_Ia	Founder of Züritrail, a Swiss Association of bikers	Not officially involved in the process	Representative of bikers, knowledge of parts of the process	2018, 2 h
	ZI_Ib				2023, 1 h
Zurich	ZI_IIa	Representative of Swiss Competence Center for Accident Prevention	Officially involved in the process	Representative for legal liabilities, trail route, conflicts, knowledge of process	2018, 1 h
	ZI_I Ib				2023, 35 min
Zurich	ZI_III	Decision-maker from Grün Stadt Zürich (owner of the forest)	Leader of process	Representative of forest owner and public authority. Leader of the process, knowledge of process	2018, 2 h
Vienna	VI_Ia	Founding member of WienerWaldTrails	Fully involved in process	Representative of bikers, knowledge of process	2018, 2 h
	VI_Ib				2023, 2 h
Vienna	VI_IIa	Founding member of WienerWaldTrails	Fully involved in process	Representative of bikers, knowledge of process	2018, 1hr
	VI_I Ib				2023, 30 min
Vienna	VI_III	Representative of main forest owner association (in terms of territory size) Austrian State Forests (ÖbF).	Fully involved in process	Representative of forest owner and semi-public authority, knowledge of process	2021, 1.5 h
Vienna	VI_IV	Representative of UNESCO-Austrian Biosphere Reserve Wienerwald Management GmbH	Fully involved in process	Representative of environmental concerns, knowledge of process	2021, 1.5 h

3.3. Ethics

We followed the ethical considerations for qualitative research by ensuring the informed consent via signed data protection sheets of our interview partners. We have anonymized the personal data of the interviewees and ensured the interview partners' confidentiality by not making their answers traceable to a single individual. We engaged these actors at the community level several times (which takes a considerable amount of time), including walking tours on the trails in one case. This made us reflect on our own roles as researchers and our behavior as data collection instruments in these interview situations. We made sure to follow the interview guides (see Supplementary Material to this article), and we conducted the analysis interpretation systematically along the

lines of the developed categories.

4. Results

4.1. Genesis of the process: new arrangements in innovation development

The innovation process has been outlined in our theory section as the emergence of new arrangements in societal interactions for addressing emerging problems (Grimm et al., 2013). The development of the **Biketrial Triemli** started in 1998 because mountain bikers rode both on and off forest paths across the Uetliberg area creating several illegal trails even though the Federal Forest Law prohibited mountain bikers for riding within in the forests. From 1998 to 2005, the number of bikers

using and building illegal trails increased drastically, posing challenges to forest managers and forest owners and leading to conflicts between forest users (e.g., walkers, hikers, joggers, families with small children). The peak of the disputes was in 2000 and it took until 2005 to come to an agreement for the first concept:

“2000 was the high point of the disputes. In 2004 a first part of the trail was banned. 2005 we reached the concept with the rules that still apply.” (INT_ZI_Iib 17.31’)

By the end of 2000, bikers had added infrastructure, such as wooden ramps, jumps and drops, to the illegal trails without seeking permission from forest owners and managers or applying for a building permit. In parallel, several other stakeholders started complaining about the bikers, including residents of Friesenberg (the district next to Uetliberg), tourists using the train to go to Uetliberg, archaeologists, gamekeepers of the region, the hiking association from Friesenberg, the community of Stallikon, the ETH forester who were by that time also forest owners and others. As one interviewee states, nature protection and any citizen who walked through became concerned: *“We have Pro Natura, Pro Uetliberg, Birdlife, basically every concerned citizen who walks through and sees what’s going on is basically also a stakeholder.”* (INT_ZI_Iib. 25.34’)

Overall, the conflict in the Uetliberg area was unresolved, and the topic became sensitive. Therefore, several stakeholders sent letters of complaint to the city government, represented by Grün Stadt Zürich (GSZ), which is the largest owner and manager of the Uetliberg forest. Additionally, one member of the neighborhood association and the right-wing party Schweizerische Volkspartei (SVP) began lobbying against bikers in public, pressuring the city government to address the situation.

Subsequently, GSZ initiated the negotiation process in 2005. As soon as GSZ began the negotiations, the right-wing party withdrew from the negotiation process. In the first meeting, which involved all concerned stakeholders except the bikers using the trail, a proposal was made to ban bikers from the Uetliberg area. However, the Swiss police, who played a crucial role in the negotiation process, disagreed and stopped the meeting until a feasible solution was found.

As a result, a task group comprising representatives of GSZ (mainly forest managers), ETH Zurich and the organization Swiss Cycling was created. This group developed a utilization concept called “Hiking and biking in the Uetliberg.” In this concept, they proposed to legalize two trails: the Biketrail Triemli and the Biketrail Höckler. They also proposed closing some roads for bikers, improving signalization of the roads and banning bikers from using the local train between Uetikon Waldegg and Uetliberg stations. After a three-year trial period, the concept was fully implemented in 2008. Additionally, further measures were taken: First, other illegal trail constructions were removed. Second, GSZ covered the costs for the legalization and maintenance of the trail. Third, the working group continued to meet regularly to discuss trade-offs for other forest users in the Uetliberg area. Last, several informational events were organized to inform the public about the situation and the measures taken between 2005 and 2008. During the whole negotiation process, bikers were represented indirectly by one Swiss delegate, who was himself a biker, as there was no formal biker’s association in Uetliberg at that time.

In the 1990s (Phase I), legal **mountain bike trails in the Vienna woods** were developed using only existing forest roads and very short sections of hiking trails (referred to as shared trails). About twenty years later (Phase II), a trail net of illegal biking trails in the Vienna forests had emerged. This was due to the unattractive forest roads that were open for the sport:

“The mountain bikers had no legal routes they would like to use. The landowners, especially from the forestry context, had the problem that they were confronted with a proliferation of illegal trails.” (VI_INT Ib 11.18’)

Subsequently, bikers formed an association, WienerWaldTrails

(WWT), and initiated negotiations in 2014 with the objective of “*creating an attractive network of trails for bikers*” (VI_INT 2b 4.05’).

The trail network was formalized in 2016. Since the formalization, some trails have been legalized, and new ones have been built, while others still remain under negotiation. The forests where the WienerWaldTrails are situated are owned by the city of Vienna, the Austrian Federal Forest Company (ÖBF AG), the Roman Catholic Church (Klosterneuburg Monastery), and a few small private owners. The Austrian Federal Forest Company (Öbf) manages the forest. The negotiation process for the legalization of trails (Phase II) lasted two years and involved several technical planning workshops and negotiation workshops with all relevant stakeholders (see Table 2). The meetings had an agreed framework of confidentiality:

“The conversations and meetings were emotional to varying degrees, and what was ‘on our minds’ was discussed within an agreed framework of confidentiality.” (VI_IV 34.54’)

Because of the partly emotional negotiations, all meetings and workshops were initiated and conducted by an external institution: iNUF, a private agency for developing and planning innovative nature and leisure concepts. Early in the negotiation process, Biosphärenpark Wienerwald Management GmbH (the management of the UNESCO Biosphere Reserve Vienna Woods) commissioned the agency iNUF (see Fig. 1) to develop a concept with suggestions and ideas for providing trails in the Vienna woods in accordance with the strict requirements of the biosphere reserve. The resulting study provided the basis for proactively meeting nature protection requirements and served as the foundation for the negotiation process.

Discussions and negotiations concerning revisions to existing illegal trails provided an opportunity for all stakeholders to consider the implications if the trails were not legalized. The importance of the platform is highlighted as most necessary:

“If we didn’t have this stakeholder platform with this focus and the various stakeholders involved and the various processes that were developed from this platform, [...] then it probably wouldn’t have been possible.” (VI_Ib 16.18’)

The main argument for legalizing some of the illegal trails was to prevent bikers from creating additional illegal trails. Additionally, despite very few hunting activities occurring in the Vienna woods, the high potential for conflict between hunting and biking interests was a primary argument against the legalization of trails, according to the interview partners.

“I always criticize our [Austrian] agricultural and forestry businesses for never differentiating between where we actually are located and what we are talking about. Yes, [...] mountain biking has negative effects on hunting and game. [But] that’s a completely different topic in the Vienna woods cultural area than somewhere in the Limestone Alps.” (VI_1a 01.05.27’). The hunting opposition was confirmed by another stakeholder:

“Hunting objections were brought forward by the Lower Austrian Hunters Association into the stakeholder platform discussions, who stated that the new route would go through a retreat area for animals in the forest [“Einstand” in German].” (VI_IV 12.32’)

From the perspective of the UNESCO Vienna woods biosphere management, nature conservation was not the highest obstacle at the end of the process: *“In the end it was [...] rarely nature conservation—because it was agreed and accepted from the outset that no new trails would be built in core zones.”* (VI_IV 13.44’)

After several rounds of negotiations, and because of the increasing demand for mountain bike trails, three of the WienerWaldTrails Association founding members decided to establish the firm PHAT MTB & More GmbH. Since 2018, the firm has managed to create the Trailcenter Hohe Wand Wiese (HWW), which is responsible for exploring new

routes. The routes are developed by another specialized firm, Trailaffairs, led by members of the WienerWaldTrails biking association. The trail center organizes events and “testivals” (events for testing new bikes and routes), rents bikes, operates a “biking school” for adults and children, and offers various courses for mountain bikers. According to the interviewees, the new trails network attracts bikers, who subsequently avoid illegal trails, which in turn helps the Vienna woods UNESCO-Bioserve protect the core nature protection zones (see Transcript VI_IV).

4.2. Main catalyst for starting the negotiations

Negotiations for the **Biketrial Triemli** started when conflicts between forest users escalated and an increased number of complaint letters were sent to GSZ. The president of the neighborhood association and a member of the right-wing party also increased pressure on the city council. In the case of the **WienerWaldTrails** (Phase II), the main starting point was the growing number of illegal trails in the Vienna woods. Forest owners realized they were liable in case of accidents on their property and were also concerned about damages to the trees. Similarly, actors from the WWF and the biosphere reserve perceived bikers as a threat to the protective functions of nature, biodiversity and wildlife in the area. Additionally, the hikers’ organizations (ÖTK) were uncomfortable with mountain bikers using the hiking trails illegally.

4.3. Actors’ involvement in social innovation

As outlined in our theoretical section, the concept of social innovation emphasizes a stronger role of civil society actors in decision-making processes. So far, the forestry sector has been described as a very closed community, where decision-making rests with determined forestry actors (Kubeczko et al., 2006). The actors’ involvement in both negotiation processes encompass a range of public and civil society organizations. They extend beyond the forest authorities, forest owners and forest managers, who are the highest-ranking officials responsible, as their official permission is required for any construction or legalization. By law they would be the highest-ranking and sole parties responsible. Under other conditions and in other circumstances, this would have been the case here as well.

The following table (Table 3) presents our results on the main actors involved in the legalization processes, their institutional backgrounds and their main interests and concerns.

As shown in Table 3, the number of actors involved in both processes amounts to 31. The table illustrates three key findings: First, some groups of actors, like the NGOs, have similar concerns, including nature protection and damage done to the forest in both areas. Second, the interested groups have different reasons for opposing biking: the public authorities’ goals are more solution-oriented. This is understandable, as they appear to have been under pressure from several sides, which is also reflected in the listed concerns (Table 3). Third, the majority of forestry sector actors (owners and managers) opposed biking most strictly. However, the concerned municipal departments and public administration (#8–11 and #25–29, summed up as “public authorities”) were important during the process; as partial owners, they held many decision-making powers regarding land use in the area.

Finally, where the identified concerns and interests are similar, the role and importance of actors in the processes differs. In the Vienna case, the biking association (#21, see Table 3) played a crucial role, whilst, in the Zurich case, bikers were not involved in the process, as they were not organized in an association at that time. In Zurich, in contrast, it was the local government that played a crucial role in fostering a feasible solution, ensuring that biking was not banned from the Uetliberg area.

4.4. Negotiation outcome, solutions found, success and compromises

In the main outcome, **Biketrial Triemli** successfully negotiated two

Table 3
Actors’ institutional background and main interests/concerns (information based on interviews).

Biketrial Triemli (CH)		WienerWaldTrails (AT)	
Actors’ institutional background	Main interests/ concerns	Actors’ institutional background	Main interests/ concerns
FOREST OWNERS AND MANAGERS			
#1 ETH Zurich	#1 Wanted to have a solution that is optimal for all parties involved	#15 City of Vienna	#15 Wanted to have an offer for recreational use for the Viennese mountain bikers
#2 Canton of Zurich (through Grün Stadt Zürich)	#2 Assumed responsibility of initiating the process (as they received complains if conflicts rose in the Uetliberg area)	#16 Austrian Federal Forest Company	#16 Wanted to have a solution for the conflictful situation while not damaging the forest
#3 ETH forester	#3 Was against bikers and would have preferred to ban biking in the Uetliberg area	#17 Klosterneuburg Monastery	#17 & # 18 Wanted to have a solution for their properties and were against bikers
#4 Grün Stadt Zürich Forester	#4 Wanted a solution optimal for all parties involved	#18 A few small private owners	
COLLECTIVE ORGANIZATIONS (NGO)			
#5 Hiking association	#5 Were against mountain bikers because they use forest and hiking roads without respecting other forest users	#19 Lower Austrian Hunters Association (who officially participated in the biggest final stakeholder dialogue at the end of the process); some interested hunters were individually involved and participated in the negotiations	#19 Was against bikers and would have preferred to ban biking in the Wienerwald area
#6 Neighborhood association	#6 Were against bikers as they use with their dirty bikes a private road to reach the closest train station for traveling to the top of the Uetliberg	#20 Austrian Tourist Club (ÖTK)	#20 Wanted a solution for the conflict between their hikers and bikers (ÖTK is mainly a hikers’ interest organization)
#7 Beautification association	#7 Were concerned about the Uetliberg and the impact bikers have on it	#21 Wienerwald MTB trails association (for Phase II) #22 Lower Austrian tourist agency Wienerwald Tourism GmbH #23 Biosphere Reserve Wienerwald (Biosphere Reserve)	#21 Wanted a solution to be able to bike (legally) and to end the conflict #22 Wanted to create income for the communities of Lower Austria via tourists that stay overnight and go biking (federal province of Lower Austria) #23 & # 24 Wanted to protect the

(continued on next page)

Table 3 (continued)

Biketrial Triemli (CH)		WienerWaldTrails (AT)	
Actors' institutional background	Main interests/concerns	Actors' institutional background	Main interests/concerns
		Wienerwald Management GmbH #24 World Wide Fund for Nature (WWF)	biosphere reserve
PUBLIC AUTHORITIES (POLICY, GOVERNMENT AND ADMINISTRATION)			
#8 City council	#8 The right-wing party put pressure on them to propose a solution to the problem	#25 Provincial administration of Lower Austria	#25 Wanted income for the region
#9 Neighboring community Stallikon	#9 Were concerned about the current situation and the effects that this development could have on their community and forests	#26 Government of Vienna (please note that Vienna is both a city and province)	#26 Wanted recreational offerings for its citizens
#10 Department for Archaeology and Monument Conservation of the Canton of Zurich	#10 Wanted to protect the archaeological site of Uetliberg by banning biking	#27 Forest Department [MA49]	#27 Wanted a solution that did not damage the trees
#11 Zurich city police	#11 Wanted a feasible solution that satisfied all parties involved	#28 Sports Department [MA51] #29 Tourism Department of the City of Vienna	#28 Wanted recreational offerings for its citizens #29 Wanted to attract mountain bike tourism
OTHER PRINCIPAL ACTORS			
#12 Right-wing party (SVP)	#12 Stated through a complaint in the city council that the situation had to end; mentioned that the city was not taking steps to prevent biking. Believed the city council was responsible and had to propose a solution. Stopped complaints after negotiation process started.	In the Austrian case no other type of principal actors were involved in key functions in the negotiation process	
#13 Game keeper	#13 Was concerned bikers disturbing wild animals in the Uetliberg area and destroying their habitat		
#14 The Sihltal-Zürich-Uetliberg (SZU) train	#14 Were concerned about bikers using the train to travel to Uetliberg, leaving the train dirty and disturbing other passengers		
BIKERS			
In the Swiss case, bikers were not involved in the negotiation process.		#21 Wienerwald MTB trails association (for	#21, #30 & #31 Wanted a solution to be

Table 3 (continued)

Biketrial Triemli (CH)		WienerWaldTrails (AT)	
Actors' institutional background	Main interests/concerns	Actors' institutional background	Main interests/concerns
#31 Trailaffairs (Phase II)		Phase II, see "NGOs" above). #30 PHAT MTB & More GmbH (private firm that organizes sporting events, founded by bikers during the negotiations in 2016, and now operating the Trailcenter HWW, Phase II)	able to bike (legally) and to end the conflict

single tracks to be used exclusively by bikers. According to our interviews, the solutions were found because most concerns of all stakeholders involved were addressed. "I think that nowadays a large proportion of people use the official trails." (ZI_Ib 47.12) "I have to say that we have the 80,000 descents on the trail and when I see that, it can't be that rubbish to ride." (ZI_III 17.31)

In the case of the **WienerWaldTrails**, two built trails and seven shared trails (shared with hikers on hiking paths) were negotiated. The path to solutions was not easy and was made jointly possible only through involvement of all partners for one common goal:

"All in all, the persistence of all the partners represented in the platform to stick with the issue and achieve a joint success was crucial, even despite all the differences of opinion and heated discussions." (VI_III 17.36)

The solutions found resulted in satisfactory compromises concerning the flow of mountain bike traffic, the relief and protection of sensitive zones with high environmental values, and a more attractive offer for recreational users. "We have developed a really impressive network of single tracks and shared trails. Some of which can only be used by mountain bikers, while others are shared with hikers and other user groups. It has worked very, very well from many perspectives. Including from the point of view of hunters and nature conservation." (INT VI_Iib 54.03)

Fig. 3 provides an overview of the main actors' involvement in the final outcome of the negotiations, as well as the funding strategies identified in the analysis of each case.

Fig. 3 shows the differences in the main interactions and negotiations, the principal stakeholders involved and the differences in final funding strategies.

In Vienna, the negotiations centered on discussions between bikers with hikers, hunters and biosphere reserve representatives. In Zurich the negotiations centered on the issue of how to fulfill the recreational demand and the technical requirements for trail building. "The last third had to be completely redone once — it wasn't a sustainable trail due to erosion. ... [It] was just poorly built and had to be rebuilt. Now it is heavily graveled and includes many switchback turns." (INT ZI_Iib 5.39)

The range of principal stakeholders involved differs between the cases. In Vienna, it was only the forest authorities who made decisions in Phase I, while in Phase II there were many more stakeholders in decision-making roles during the negotiations on the new trails. In Zurich, similar stakeholders (owners, managers, a political party and the public administration) were active; in Austria, also, bikers and representatives from the Biosphere Reserve were involved as principal stakeholders (Fig. 3).

4.5. Funding strategies

Funding turned out to be a most decisive factor for maintenance of the trails. As a result of the negotiations, Biketrial Triemli is financed by

Fig. 3. Mapping of actors, negotiations and funding strategies for mountain bike trails in the Vienna and Zurich forests.

GSZ (Fig. 3), which is responsible because the trail is situated on its land. GSZ assumed all the costs for the legalization of the trail and still covers all maintenance costs. The biker association, funded in 2010, now assists with some maintenance activities. No bikers have to pay for using the trail. In contrast, the Wienerwald trails employ different and complex solutions. First, as an outcome in the negotiations, it is not the forest owners (part of which is the City of Vienna) but the biking association that covers the maintenance and operating costs for the two single tracks built in Phase II. The biking association receives funding through membership fees and support from the volunteer work of their members. Additionally, it secures funding through sponsorships and other activities they organize. Second, the Austrian Tourist Club (ÖTK) covers the costs for maintaining the seven shared trails. Third, forest owners in the area where the trails pass, receive a levy of approximately 0.26 cents per meter per annum from the Wienerwald Tourismus GmbH.

4.6. Future prospects

In the Uetliberg area, most bikers have been steered into two single tracks. However, as demand continues to grow and the needs of bikers change, GSZ decided to improve the current trails by expanding them. Initially, bikers were once again not involved in the negotiation process because GSZ assumes responsibility and costs for the trail. According to the most recent interviews, the bikers' association and GSZ now cooperate.

In the Vienna woods, the number of illegal trails has currently diminished. The bikers' association and related firms founded by active bikers now include the critical mass of former bikers who were using an extensive network of illegal bike trails. There is no public funding, but finances are one crucial issue (Fig. 3) for future prospects, and some interview partners mention the burden this implies for the volunteers and the need for better resources:

"[Public authorities said] spend the club budget on getting it [the MBT] built. Make sure it's maintained. In other words, it simply needs professionalization if you say, okay, you want to establish mountain biking in the region. You want to market it. Everything that happens. Then I think we simply need more resources and not just the endeavors of many individual volunteers. To keep it stable in the long term." (INT VI_Ib 1.06.42)

Currently, mountain bikers of all types are using the new offerings. But there is a need to explore new trail routes and possibilities to accommodate the current transformations in mountain biking. The mountain biking sport is rapidly developing, with new trends like e-

biking, which now allows for faster speeds uphill, gravel biking (a more flexible and universal technique) and bike packing (trekking for longer time periods).

5. Discussion

The analysis of both initiatives reveals several main features of social innovation and the response to societal demands conceptualized above: Both cases represent innovations addressing societal challenges (Mulgan, 2012; Sinclair & Baglioni, 2014), leading to a reconfiguration of societal practices (Howaldt & Kopp, 2012) and providing insights into the role of civil society actors and their inclusion as an essential part of social innovation (Polman et al., 2017). In the years before the negotiations, before the negotiations, the importance of civil society actors such as bikers was usually not considered by the forest authorities. Decisions were taken top-down within the forestry actors' group (Boerboom & Ferretti, 2014; Hogl et al., 2016). The participation of more stakeholders and civil society actors in the negotiations particularly led to new forms of conflict negotiation and resulted in less hierarchical decision-making processes (North, 1990; Ostrom, 1990). Additionally, new institutional and financial solutions were negotiated (North, 1990).

The results differ from other studies that have shown how well coproduction of volunteers, public authorities and professional trail builders can lead to successful solutions, including in terms of the trail building itself (Iversen et al., 2024). Such coproduction did not take place in the trail-building phase: While in the Vienna case the trail-building itself was fully up to the bikers,³ in the Swiss case a professional firm was hired and paid by GSZ. Both results show the differences and communalities in how final solutions were achieved and carried out.

The common pattern across both cases is clearly that negotiations started because the current situation was not acceptable to some users. However, the cases differ in the catalyst for their negotiations, the initiator of the negotiations, the funding strategies and their future prospects (Gutmann & Thompson, 2002). In the Austrian case, bikers organized themselves by creating a formal association to interact as the leading partner, whereas in the Swiss case, it was the city council, represented by GSZ and under high political pressure, that initiated the process. While a bundle of stakeholders was involved in both negotiation

³ The bikers built the negotiated trails within several weeks by themselves, organized in seven volunteer groups of 15 people, each steered by a "group leader."

processes, our study revealed that in the Swiss case, bikers were not included until recently. Consequently, the concerns and wishes of this stakeholder category were not considered in the negotiations.

In the Austrian case, bikers, through their association, were able to represent individual bikers, act as a negotiation partner, take responsibility for financing the trails, and address the concerns of bikers. While in the Austrian case we found that a bottom-up approach led by civil society worked well in the negotiation process, in the Swiss case a top-down approach led by public actors was necessary to push the process forward. In both cases, public actors facilitated the innovation process and played a crucial role in this regard. It can be said that in both cases, the success period began with involvement of public actors who facilitated the legalization of MBT (Mayntz, 1998; Mayntz & Scharpf, 1995; Ostrom, 1990; Rhodes, 1997). By the end of the negotiations, the challenges (e.g., liability issues) that forest managers and forest owners typically face regarding such infrastructure installations were mitigated.

As shown in Tables 3 and in the Swiss case, most stakeholders had similar interests in wanting to ban mountain biking in the Uetliberg area. This could have been avoided if bikers had been integrated into the negotiation process. Fortunately, the police disagreed with this proposition, as they would have been responsible for executing prohibitions by force. Subsequently, they supported the idea of finding a solution that was feasible and acceptable for all stakeholders involved. The Austrian stakeholders were mainly concerned with the protection of the Biosphere Reserve on the one hand. This meant steering the constantly increasing illegal bike trails away from the UNESCO Biosphere Reserve Vienna Woods. On the other hand, the bikers' association wanted legal solutions that were more attractive than the normal forest roads from Phase I. Subsequently, the legalization of the trails in the Austrian case led to directing bikers away from the core zones of the Biosphere Reserve and reducing damage to nature.

In terms of funding strategies, both cases show that the maintenance of the trails is expensive. Therefore, as stated by Neumeier (2017), clarifying who will cover the costs during the negotiation process is crucial. In the Austrian case, bikers were creative in finding ways (e.g., mobilizing volunteers, finding sponsors, organizing "festivals") to cover the costs. In the Swiss case, the city council (City of Zurich) took responsibility for the costs, as they are also the owners of the forest area where the legalized trail is situated.

5.1. Strengths and limitations

A methodological strength of the study is that it outlines negotiation processes for establishing mountain bike trails with in-depth case descriptions along three crucial criteria: actors' involvement, negotiation processes, and outcomes. The approach connects specific analysis of stakeholder involvement processes with their workable agreements as outcomes.

At the same time, this points to the weaknesses of the comparative methodological design: First, both solutions were, in terms of our initial assumptions, successful. To increase validity and strengthen the results, it would be necessary to further compare the outcomes with contrasting examples where legalization could not be achieved. Understanding the reasons for failure would contribute to our inferences on success. Second, our results provide evidence for negotiation processes in similar contexts, namely multifunctional forest settings with intensive use close to touristic urban areas. The method does not allow replicability not replicable for broader generalizations to rural areas, where presumably, more industrial private owners with higher interests in economical timber production are involved.

6. Conclusions and management implications

Viewing the conflict through a social innovation lens, we conclude that involving the most important stakeholders is a crucial first step in addressing their concerns and integrating these concerns into the

negotiation process. In the cases of this study, such issues have traditionally been tackled and administered by a small circle of (mostly) forestry actors, who were unable to respond adequately to the pressure from illegal bike trails. Findings suggest that stakeholder involvement is a key characteristic of inclusive governance and management in difficult situations. First, public authorities need to recognize mountain biking as a key management concern with the need for innovative solutions. Only by considering multiple concerns and addressing them can conflicts during the negotiation process be addressed.

Second, managers should allocate responsibilities for the proposed solutions and address the interest and concerns of all involved actors. This applies not only for the legalized trails but also for the financial arrangements. Third, the legalization of mountain bike trails, if well-planned and maintained, offers opportunities for sustainable income generation for both landowners and municipalities.

Although both cases show similar outcomes in terms of compromise and responsibility for the trail, they have very different strategies for maintenance and funding, as well as different support modes from influential stakeholders. Vienna's management challenges highlight the importance of adequate public funding; in contrast, Zurich's public funding system ensures better maintenance but reduces bikers' autonomy. These differences have consequences for their future management prospects and continuation of the solutions found.

We conclude that future research should focus on the growing involvement of actors and the dynamics of stakeholder interaction, as these are key indicators for addressing the increasing societal demands on scarce natural resources and spaces such as urban forests. A more in-depth analysis of empirical cases is needed to better understand the role, power and influence of specific actors in social innovation processes. The study contributes to a better understanding of the current and future use options of the limited forest resources in times of climate-related damages (Romeiro et al., 2022) and increasing societal pressure for outdoor recreation.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Ludvig Alice: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Zivojinovic Ivana:** Writing – review & editing. **Wilkes-Allemann Jerylee:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jort.2025.100861>.

Data availability

The data that has been used is confidential.

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